

La Sfera Challenge

Team Newberry

Team Newberry will work with a version housed at the [Newberry Library Ayer MS Map 1](#)

TEAM NEWBERRY DOCUMENTS

[Transcription Portal](#)

[Project Log](#)

[Rules and Guidelines](#)

TEAM UPDATES:

Check our official (and expanded) Progress Updates [here](#).

July 7: TEAM NEWBERRY is ready to recruit! 💪👑

Suzanne Karr Schmidt
@DrKarrSchmidt

Like Maps? LOVE Manuscripts?

Join Team Newberry to transcribe our gorgeous c. 1425 La Sfera and win major international bragging rights! This virtual competition runs July 17 to 31, 2020.
[#medievaltwitter](#) [@isamagni](#) [@italpaleography](#)
[@NewberryLibrary](#)

Team Newberry
Team Newberry will work with a version housed at the Newberry Library Ayer MS Map 1 TEAM NEWBERRY ...
lasferachallenge.wordpress.com

1:48 PM · Jul 7, 2020

 20 people are Tweeting about this

July 14: TEAM NEWBERRY is complete! We can't wait to sink our teeth into VAULT slipcase Ayer MS map 1!! TEAM VATICAN'S [@cebenes](#) has offered to commission a Lego rendition of our tower, courtesy of her young master builder... Given that today is Bastille Day, I see that excellent offer, and raise it! My architects choose a different medium ... let them build cake!

July 15: We could not have asked for a better start! A Big present from a Junior member of Team Vatican. AND WE LOVE IT!

Carrie Benes
@cebenes2

#LaSferaChallenge2 @DrKarrSchmidt & Team Newberry, here's a present from a junior member of Team Vatican... Dati's version of the Getty Quarantine Challenge, perhaps?

July 16: After a productive virtual meeting this morning, TEAM NEWBERRY is ready to start! Let the count down begin! – 1 day! 📖💻

July 19: And we present to you, *La Sfera* edible edition (Team Newberry style):

@displacermoose @evadeisoidato @NewberryLibrary

8:30 AM · Jul 19, 2020

♡ 42 👤 See Suzanne Karr Schmidt's other Tweets

Behold the HUBRIS of Cake!

July 19: Off we go! Collectively, we decided to divide the pages to transcribe equally among all team members (more or less!) with the promise that, if any of us felt it was becoming too much, we would share our concerns with the group (or the team captains) and someone else from the team would help by taking on some of the transcriptions. And here goes our first motto: **Teamwork makes the dreamwork!** 🤗

During the first week of the challenge, Team Newberry transcribed the entire manuscript. Some of the headaches? W A T E R D A M A G E S 🤗 (below f.1r)

Read about our transcribers experience in our **Progress Updates**.

July 23: Co-captain **@isamagni** is having fun exploring this deluxe copy of *La Sfera* and analyzing its (very regular!) humanistic script. Among her favorites, the scribe's very classy *poggiano* style *g* made of two rounds connected by a vertical line:

How beautiful! The Newberry *Sfera* is clearly a luxury copy, written on vellum by a professional scribe in a very regular humanistic hand, characterized by thin strokes and round letter forms. Made of (only!) two fascicles (1¹² 2¹²). And YES! We also got a very elegant, vertical catchword (f.12v):

July 24: Co-captain (and art historian) Suzanne is on a mission to discover WHO commissioned this manuscript? Who are you, wealthy patron? We've got no luck so far. But it isn't over! (Coat of arms, f.1r)

In the meantime, our fantastic squad has started the first phase of revisions. See their impressions in our **Progress Updates**.

July 30: AND we are off towards the finish line! After our reviewers did a splendid job revising each other's pages, editors and co-captains Isabella and Suzanne took on the final editing phase: Isabella edited and signed off on the text(s) and Suzanne edited and signed off on the many illustrations included in our manuscript. Of course, while focusing more on one of the two aspects (textual or visual), we both checked the entirety of the manuscript. Suzanne, for example, caught a missing initial on f.7r (that Isabella had missed! OUCH! 🙄🙄). And here goes our second Team motto: *chi va piano, va sano e va lontano!*

AND we are DONE! Allow us to conclude with a **BIG SHOUT OUT** to all our team members. Every single one of them brought enthusiasm, competence and intellectual curiosity to the group and to the project. None of us had transcribed *La Sfera* before, and only one of us (Isabella) had worked with **From the Page** before. It was quite a learning experience for all of us and the two co-captains couldn't be prouder of the Team! Bravissim* ragazz*!!! ~ *Co-Captains Isabella & Suzanne*

#TEAMNEWBERRY members include:

- Isabella Magni, Rutgers University, Co-Captain ([@isamagni](#) and [@italpaleography](#))
- Suzanne Karr Schmidt, Newberry Library, Co-Captain ([@DrKarrSchmidt](#))
- Erasmo Castellani, Duke University
- Eva del Soldato, University of Pennsylvania ([@evadelsoldato](#))
- Daniela D'Eugenio, Vanderbilt University
- Jesse Hurlbut, Independent Scholar ([@jessehurlbut](#))
- Sarah Iovan, Independent Scholar ([@displacermoose](#))
- Ilona Klein, Brigham Young University
- Lia Markey, Newberry Library
- Samantha Mattocci, Independent Scholar

TEAM NEWBERRY is sponsored by the [Center for Renaissance Studies at the Newberry Library](#).

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